

Efficient Model Loading through Static Analysis

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Abstract—Growing model sizes reveal scalability issues in the current generation of model management tools and technologies. Hence, there is a demand for more sophisticated mechanisms for execution engines of model management languages to make the most efficient use of the available system resources. In this paper, we present an approach to enable execution engines of model management programs to load models partially and just keep the necessary parts of the model in memory for as long as they are needed. This approach leverages sophisticated static analysis of model management programs to load only relevant model elements instead of naively loading the entire models into memory. In this way, the proposed approach aspires to enable model management programs to process models faster with a reduced memory footprint compared to naive complete model loading which is the current state of the art.

Index Terms—Partial Loading, Model Partitioning, Memory Management, Model-Driven Engineering

I. PROBLEM

As using model-driven engineering (MDE) is getting popular for large projects, dealing with large models becomes more crucial. In MDE, models are manipulated using model management programs and execution engines of these programs should be able to manage large models efficiently in terms of memory and time. Efficient resource management plays an important role, in order to reduce the cost of execution, particularly when the execution engines use pay-as-you-go resources.

Therefore, the growing size of models is a challenge for the current technologies and tools in model-driven engineering such as Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF) and it pushes them into their limits. The way that they interact with models is a primary reason of these limitations.

For example, consider a large model that conforms to the IMDB metamodel (a subset of IMDB metamodel is shown in Figure 1), and on which we wish to evaluate a constraint to validate model elements. This constraint could be written in a model validation language such as the Epsilon Validation Language (EVL)¹ [1] as shown in Listing 1.

In Listing 1, there is one constraint which validates all instances of *Movie*. This constraint, *hasTitle*, checks that the *title* of all instances of *Movie* in the model has a value and it is not equal to *null*. The constraint shown in Listing 1 only

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¹<https://www.eclipse.org/epsilon/doc/evl/>

Fig. 1. A part of IMDB Metamodel

Listing 1. An EVL constraint for checking the title of movies

```
1 model Imdb driver EMF {
2 nsuri = "http://movies"
3 };
4 context Movie {
5 constraint hasTitle {
6 check: self.title<> null
7 }
8 }
```

accesses the *title* attribute of *Movie* and no other elements of the IMDB model.

In this case, when a model management program needs to load and validate the model:

- If the model is file-based (e.g. XMI), as the EVL execution engine does not know in advance which parts of the model the program will access, the entire model needs to be loaded into memory.
- If the model is not file-based (e.g., stored in a database-backed repository such as CDO [2] or Hawk [3]), the EVL execution engine can retrieve model elements on demand. Still, in the absence of static analysis, there is no way to tell which features of these model elements should be retrieved from the repository for each element. In this situation, there are two alternatives: either *greedily* fetch all features in advance or *lazily* fetch all features on demand.

Considering Listing 1 that uses the *title* of the *Movie* but not other attributes (e.g. *year*) or references (e.g. *persons*) (See Figure 1), the two strategies are sub-optimal:

- Greedy: The other attributes of the *Movie* (e.g. *year*) and its properties (e.g. *persons*) are fetched from the repository but are never used by the validator, thus wasting memory.
- Lazy: Multiple round-trips to the repository are re-

quired to fetch the values of the *title* attribute of each *Movie*.

The former strategy favours execution time over memory consumption, while the second strategy requires less memory, but potentially multiple round-trips to the repository (detrimental to performance).

To summarise, the general problem is that the interaction of model management program execution engines with models (file-based or repository-based) can be too “short-sighted” in the absence of static-analysis-based model loading and caching mechanisms. This limitation results in increased model loading times and unnecessary memory consumption.

This project introduces an approach that aims to enable model management programs to load only parts of models that are required for their execution and eliminate the overhead of loading unnecessary parts in memory. In this approach, by using in-advance knowledge about the program provided by static analysis, execution engines are able to identify, load and process model elements of interest only. In addition, instead of keeping elements into memory until the end of execution, the elements will be disposed from memory when they are no longer needed by the model management program.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The proposed solution provides two facilities for the execution engine to improve scalability: partial loading and intelligent partitioning.

By supporting partial loading of a model in the execution engine, it just loads the elements of the model which are necessary for executing the program and in this way, the loading time is decreased (as the number of elements to load will be less). Besides, in intelligent partitioning, models are divided into some partitions and each partition is kept while it is referenced by the program. In this way, instead of loading model elements greedily or lazily (see Section I), one partition of the model will be loaded in each trip to repository or file and instead of keeping elements till the end of execution, each partition will be held in memory while it is referenced by the program (disposal facility). Therefore, by providing partial loading of model and intelligent partitioning, the execution engine performance will be improved in memory consumption and loading time.

The methodology that we designed for developing these two facilities based on the Epsilon platform, is according to Figure 2. It is worth noting that since Epsilon Object Language (EOL) [4] is the core language of the Epsilon platform, our approach applies to all model management languages of the platform. Also, the underlying principles, subject to suitable technical modifications, can be applied to the other modelling languages, e.g., ATL.

The architecture of our proposed approach includes three main components (represented in grey colour) illustrated in Figure 2:

Fig. 2. The proposed architecture

A. Static Analysis

A part of the static analyser role is to analyse the program and create an abstract syntax graph of it. Static analysis of Epsilon programs started in [5] where the abstract syntax tree of an EOL program is computed, then resolution algorithms including variable resolution (e.g., resolving identifiers to their definitions) and type resolution (e.g., primitive types and collection types) are applied to derive an abstract syntax graph. Thus, using the abstract syntax graph, the static analyser can extract relevant information (i.e., types and properties accessed by the program).

The abstract syntax graph (the output of our static analyser) is used for extracting an *effective metamodel* for every model accessed by the program. The effective metamodel is a subset of the model’s original metamodel which consists only of types and properties that are likely to be accessed by the program [5] (see below).

To illustrate how every step of the approach works, we use the motivating example of Section I. Considering Listing 1, the program only requires the *title* of *Movie*; the remaining information in the model is not required for executing this program. Hence, the static analyser sets the resolved types based on metamodel. For example, the identifier “*Movie*” is resolved to the *Movie* model element type which is the context of first constraint (line 4 in Listing 1), hence for executing the program, all instances of *Movie* are required. In line 6, Listing 1 accesses *self.title*. As *self* refers to *Movie*, *title* is a property of *Movie* which is retrieved. Then, for executing the program, the titles of *Movie* instances are required. In this case, *title* is an attribute of *Movie* which is of String type.

B. Effective Metamodel Computation

The second step of the approach is extracting effective metamodels for the models involved in the program from the abstract syntax graph and passing them to the execution engine. The concept of effective metamodel was introduced in [6]. Effective metamodels contain just the types and features which are necessary for executing the program and they are constructed based on an algorithm that uses the resolved types of expressions.

The structure of effective metamodels is presented in Figure 3. It consists of two classes: an *EffectiveMetamodel* class with *name* and *nsuri* attributes and an *EffectiveType* class with a *name*, *attributes* and *references*. The *EffectiveMetamodel*

class connects to an *EffectiveType* by *allOfKind*, *allOfType* and *types* references.

allOfKind and *allOfType* specify the instances of types that should be loaded. The difference between these two references is that *allOfKind* is used when all instances of a class (including subclasses) should be loaded. In contrast, *allOfType* reference means only the elements of the class (without considering its subclasses) must be considered to load. The *types* reference is used for specifying classes that should be loaded when they appear in containment references of interest.

For every class used in the program (such as *Movie*), an *Effective Type* is created in the respective effective metamodel. The *effective Type* contains collections of *attributes* and *references* that reflect the attributes and references of the type accessed by the program.

Figure 4 illustrates the effective metamodel of the model validated using the EVL constraint from our motivating example (Listing 1). There is an algorithm that is used to extract this effective metamodel from EVL constraints such as that shown in Listing 1. This algorithm considers the called properties of model elements in the program and the operations such as “all” and “allInstances” that are called by model elements to detect effective types and properties and add them to the effective metamodel.

The attributes of *EffectiveMetamodel* class are filled by the information from the original metamodel, which are the *name* and namespace *URI* (i.e., unique ID of the metamodel in terms of EMF terminology) of the metamodel. In Listing 1, *Movie* is the context of constraint (line 4) which means that all instances of *Movie* should be loaded for evaluation by the program. Hence, an *effective type* is created for *Movie* and it is connected to *EffectiveMetamodel* class by *allOfKind* reference. Besides, in line 6, as *self.title* is a called property of a model element (*Movie*), the property (*title*), is considered as an attribute of *Movie*, and it is added to the attributes collection of *Movie* effective type.

1) *Discussion*: Our proposed algorithm visits the abstract syntax graph to consider all statements and expressions in it. Thus, constructing the effective metamodel highly relies on the resolved types which are set in the abstract syntax graph by the static analyser.

In EOL, there is a variable definition which is not declared the type of variable explicitly, and it uses only the *var* keyword to define a variable. This variable type is set to *Any* and all kinds of data types can be assigned to the object which holds *Any* as its type.

For example, in Listing 2, in the first line, all instances of *Actor* in the model are assigned to the *actors* variable. As *actors* is defined by *var* keyword, the resolved type of *actors* is considered as *Any* (not a model element) but because of the operation which is called in line 1 by *Actor.all()*, *Actor* is added to effective metamodel as an *Effective Type*. The situation is the same for *actresses* variable. In line 3, *objects* variable is defined by *var* keyword, thus it is considered as “Any”.

Therefore, our algorithm does not detect the type of *objects.first()* as a model element in line 6 (as the type of *objects* is “Any”) and it does not consider the *name* attribute as a candidate to add to *Actor* and *Actress* attributes in effective metamodel. Thus, the effective metamodel consists of two effective types (*Actor* and *Actress* considering the called operations in line 1 and line 2) with empty collections of attributes.

Hence, due to the dependency of effective metamodel extraction algorithm on resolved type, when the resolved type is not set **explicitly**, static analyser and effective metamodel extraction algorithm should handle this situation. Although the basic algorithm was introduced in [7] had a strong assumptions including strongly typed model management programs, we designed an advanced algorithm and took a new strategy called *greedy safe* strategy.

The way that greedy safe strategy behaves to handle the expressions which are not unambiguously typed is adding the called property (*name* in this example) to all effective types that are already added to the effective metamodel (such as *Actor* and *Actress*). Thus, by adding the called property to all of effective types in the effective metamodel (as their properties), all possibilities of retrieving this specific property will be covered.

Therefore, based on the greedy safe strategy, the effective metamodel extraction algorithm considers the *name* attribute for all effective types in the effective metamodel and adds *name* to the *Actor* and *Actress* effective types of the effective metamodel (See Figure 4).

Of course, we may end up loading properties of types that are unnecessary for executing the program (if the first element of objects is an actor, then we also load the name of the actresses, which is not required), but by loading them, we are on the safe side to not miss any part of the model that is required for executing. Using this strategy, we expect that, loading more properties will be more efficient compared to loading the entire model.

However, there are still some limitations in this algorithm. For instance, dead code (e.g. user-defined operations in EVL that are never called) will be considered for generating effective metamodels, which is not optimal. These improvements

Fig. 3. The structure of effective metamodel [6]

Fig. 4. Effective metamodel of EVL code (Listing 1)

can be considered as future work to make our algorithm more reliable and robust.

Listing 2. EOL example code

```
1 var actors = Actor.all();
2 var actresses = Actress.all();
3 var objects : Collection;
4 objects.add(actor);
5 objects.add(actress);
6 objects.first().name.println();
```

C. Partial Parser

The next step is using a partial parser for loading large models. In the case of file-based models, an initial version of a parser that can partially load XMI models was introduced in [6]. Hence, in our approach, once the effective metamodels of the different XMI models accessed by a program have been computed, the next step is to make them available to the partial XMI parser.

The repository-based models are stored in backend databases and the structure of these models is different from file-based models. Then, in our approach, the execution engine will use a strategy to load models from the repository based on the effective metamodel (Epsilon provides a driver² for loading models that are stored in CDO repository but it is based on CDO loading policies (greedily or lazily)). In addition, an algorithm is required to partition the large models. Then, in each trip to the repository, a part of the model needed for executing the program will be loaded into memory. When the loaded partition is no longer referenced by the program, a garbage collector unloads that partition from memory and keeps space for other parts of models necessary for executing the rest of the program.

III. RELATED WORK

To achieve partial loading, some of the related work use database-backed instead of file-based model persistence technologies. The most mature ones are CDO [2], Morsa [8] and NeoEMF [9]. Table I summarises some key features of these works that makes the comparison easy.

The Connected Data Object (CDO) is a model repository for EMF models. Metamodels and models can be stored in all kinds of database backends, including major relational databases (e.g. MySQL) and NoSQL databases (e.g. Neo4j). Scalability in CDO is achieved by object loading based on on-demand strategies and caching the objects in the application. Hence, it does not keep the objects which are no longer referenced by the application, and they are garbage-collected from memory automatically.

Morsa is a persistence solution for storing and accessing large models based on on-demand strategies, which is supported by its underlying NoSQL database. In Morsa, choosing the cache policy is manual, and the user should select the policy using a GUI [8]. Overall, Morsa satisfies some of the

scalability requirements such as load on demand and cache policies, but it is just a prototype, and there is no indication that its developers plan to consider crucial issues like security in order to deploy this prototype in an industrial context [10].

NeoEMF is a persistence layer for EMF models. NeoEMF is similar to Morsa in several aspects (notably in on-demand loading), but NeoEMF uses graph-databases (Morsa is supported by a document-oriented database) and it aims at exploiting the optimized navigation performance (offered by graph-databases). While NeoEMF is a more performant alternative to XMI due to high-performance access and on-demand loading, its raw performance does not surpass a more mature solution like CDO [11].

SmartSAX is another prototype that was introduced in [6]. It supports partial loading of XMI model files. SmartSAX currently does not support loading models that are persisted in multiple XMI files. Also, it does not support garbage collection to unload unnecessary parts of the model from memory.

In [12], Daniel et al. proposed PrefetchML, a domain-specific language that describes prefetching and caching rules over models. PrefetchML is a suitable solution to improve query execution time on top of scalable model persistence frameworks. The rules to describe the event conditions to activate prefetching, the objects to prefetch, and the customisation of the cache policy are defined by designers in PrefetchML.

Although recent research has made advancements in this area, existing solutions have apparent shortcomings in accessing and processing large models. As it is summarised in Table I, none of the approaches supports analyzing model management programs in order to load models based on demand. In some of these works such as PrefetchML and Morsa, end-user should set prefetching and cache policies manually. For other ones such as CDO or NeoEMF, partial loading is based on lazy strategy (Discussed in Section I).

To summarise, in the approaches that work with file-based models, some tools are based on EMF and the common format for storing models is XMI. Hence, there is a need for partial access to XMI models, which loads models using on-demand strategies using in-advance knowledge of the program instead of specifying by the user. Repositories such as Morsa, CDO provide remote accessing to large models and store them in a graph-based or relational database, but in the absence of static analysis, greedy and lazy strategies are not efficient.

IV. EXPECTED CONTRIBUTION

The main contribution of this project is execution engines for Epsilon model management languages that can handle large models efficiently in terms of memory footprint and loading time. In summary the contributions that we expect are:

- An algorithm for extracting necessary parts of the model automatically to execute the program
- An algorithm for partitioning the large models consumed by the model management programs to some partitions
- An approach for loading repository-based models partially

²<https://github.com/epsilon-labs/emc-cdo>

TABLE I
RELATED WORK COMPARISON

Research	Lazy Loading	Database Back-end	Analysis	Disposal Facility	File-based model
CDO	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
Morsa	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
XMI default parser	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
NeoEMF	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
PrefetchML	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓

V. CURRENT PROGRESS AND NEXT STEPS

We presented a new approach that will enable execution engines to eliminate the overhead of loading unimportant parts of models and of unnecessarily keeping obsolete parts (i.e. parts that have already been processed and are guaranteed not to be reaccessed) in memory in model management programs. The proposed approach has three main steps which were published in a workshop paper [13].

We started to work on the Epsilon framework [14] as it consists of a family of model management languages. Hence, when a facility is implemented for the core language (EOL), it is easily extendable for other languages.

As the first step was related to static analysis, in the context of the preliminary work which introduced Epsilon Object language analyser [5], we have added new features to the EOL static analyser to get more information such as return type compatibility, and type compatibility of context and parameters. Also, we extended EOL static analysis facility for Epsilon Validation Language (EVL) and Epsilon Transformation Language (ETL).

Then, according to the designed approach, we use a static analyser for extracting the effective metamodels. We designed and implemented an algorithm for extracting the effective metamodel to detect relevant model elements starting from the incomplete algorithm introduced in [6]. The designed algorithm supports ETL and EVL programs.

Also, for supporting XMI models in our approach, we use the parser presented in [6]. This parser requires a description of the effective metamodels to load XMI models partially. Hence, using the new algorithm, we automatically extract effective metamodels (based on static analysis of the program) and use the parser to load XMI models efficiently.

Now, we are working to support partial loading for repository-based models as well. We are considering different options such as NeoEMF or CDO as the next step for supporting partial loading of large models.

Considering the second phase of this project, which is intelligent partitioning of models, there is a need for finding an algorithm to divide the large models manipulated by model management programs into some partitions and load required partitions of the model efficiently. This algorithm would be useful in the way that enables the engine to remove elements that are no longer used from memory and only keep parts that are required for executing the rest of the program.

Hence, according to the plan illustrated in Table II, we expect that the partial loading phase will be finished till end of

second year and intelligent partitioning phase could be started in the last year of my PhD.

TABLE II
PROJECT TIME-LINE

Task	Time
Literture review	Sep 2019 - Jan 2020
Static analysis	Nov 2019 - April 2020
Effective metamodel extraction	May 2020 - April 2021
Partial loading of XMI models	August 2020 - May 2021
Partial loading of repository-based models	Jun 2021 - Oct 2021
Model partitioning	Nov 2021 - April 2022
Disposal facility	Jan 2022 - April 2022
Writing thesis, submission and defence	Feb 2022 - Sep 2022

VI. PLANS FOR EVALUATION AND VALIDATION

In order to evaluate the project, partial loading of file-based models, we will compare the new approach to other related works like the XMI partial parser. Then, the efficiency of partial loading facility will be measured considering static analysis and automated extraction of the effective metamodels.

Considering the repository-based models, we plan to evaluate our approach compared to mature approaches like NeoEMF and CDO. Since this work's goal is to reduce the time of loading and memory footprint when model management tasks are executed on large models, memory footprint and loading time are the factors that we will compare by running model management programs with and without the intelligent model partitioning and disposal facilities.

We have considered the models proposed in the GraBaTs 2009 contest for evaluation [15]. The models conform to the Java metamodel. There are five models, from Set0 to Set4, each one larger than its predecessor (from a 8.8MB XMI file with 70447 model elements representing 14 Java classes to a 646MB file with 4961779 model elements representing 5984 Java classes). Besides, we plan to consider some industrial test cases in real projects for evaluating the new approach.

Regarding correctness, we will validate all models by executing each program with all approaches and verify that the output produced by all execution pairs should be equivalent (e.g. in the number of satisfied and unsatisfied constraints in EVL or the same generated target model in ETL).

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